

Special Coordinates $v=x/t$, Special Relativity and Free Particle Actions

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Aug. 3, 2022

In a previous note (1) we discussed a transformation which changes (p =momentum=0, m_0 =rest energy) and $(x=0, t)$ to p', E' and x', t' such that $x'/t' = v$. In general, $v = \Delta x / \Delta t$ so we investigate why $x'/t' = v$ and argue that this special set of x, t is linked to the special set $p=0, E=m_0$ and so transforms in the same way. In general, however, one may have any x, t for a free particle. Thus, $(x, t) = (0, t) + (x, 0)$. We argue that using the special metric which yields $(a, b) \cdot (a, b) = -aa + bb$ ensures that $(p, E) \cdot (x, 0) = 0$ so that $-Et + px = -E't' + p'x'$ such that $x'/t' = v$.

Next we consider Lagrangian theory defined by $p = dL/dv$ partial and $E = pv - L$. Using the special coordinates x', t' such that $x'/t' = v$ leads to $Lt' = -E't' + p'x'$ as discussed in (2).

Special Relativity Based on a Rest Frame

We consider special relativity for a particle with rest mass m_0 which is not moving and is located at $x=0$ and $t=t_0$. In principle t and x may take on any value, so it is arbitrary to assign $x=0$. What is the objective then in $x=0$? We argue that a particle at rest, seen from a moving frame, moves with a velocity v and has a momentum as well as new energy. We assume that momentum should be proportional to v , in fact we make the stronger assumption that $p=Ev$. We also assume that a 2×2 matrix $\begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ b_1 & b_2 \end{pmatrix}$ ((1)) transforms $(p=0, E=m_0)$.

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_2 \\ b_1 & b_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

We make no assumption about a metric or unitarity at this point. We do assume, however, that x, t also transforms according to the same matrix.

Using the rest frame vector $(p=0, E=m_0)$ $c=1$ one has:

$$P' = a_2 m_0 \quad \text{and} \quad E' = b_2 m_0 \quad ((2)) \quad \text{Thus one only needs two of the four variables in ((1)).}$$

We then assume that $p=Ev$ so that $a_2 = v b_2$.

Next we consider the two vectors $(x=0, t_0)$ and (x, t) where x and t can take on any value. $x=0$ is arbitrary, but it is special in terms of the matrix ((1)) because it transforms in the same way as p and E . In other words:

$$x'/t' = a_2 t_0 / b_2 t_0 = v \quad ((3))$$

Thus $(x=0, t_0)$ is a special rest frame 4-vector which transforms so that $x'/t' = v$.

What about the general vector (x, t) ? It transforms in a different way such that x'/t' is not v .

Consider the possibility of ((1)) being a unitary matrix such that vector dot products are invariant under a certain metric. The question is: What is this metric?

Consider $(x, t) = (x=0, t) + (x, 0)$ and the dot product $(p, E) \cdot (x, t)$.

If one wishes:

$$(p, E) \cdot (x, t) = (p, E) \cdot (x_a, t_a) \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } x_a/t_a = v$$

So that each x, t is considered to have an origin placed at x , then:

$$(x, 0) \text{ transforms to: } (a_1 x, b_1 x) \quad \text{while } (p=0, E=m_0) \text{ transforms to } (v b_2 m_0, b_2 m_0).$$

If one assumes that ((1)) is of the form:

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & va \\ va & a \end{vmatrix} \quad ((5))$$

Then: $(p, E) \cdot (x_a, t_a)$ has the pieces $ax + v a m_0$ and $vax + a m_0$.

These are the same suggesting that a minus sign is needed to ensure that:

$(x, 0) \cdot (p, E) = 0$. This then becomes the metric. To see this explicitly, consider the Lorentz matrix:

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1/\sqrt{1-vv} & v/\sqrt{1-vv} \\ v/\sqrt{1-vv} & 1/\sqrt{1-vv} \end{vmatrix} \quad ((6))$$

This may be used to transform $(p=0, E=m_0)$ and $(x, 0)$ and the dot product of the two to yield 0 under the metric yielding $-Et + px$.

One may show that under this metric: $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $p = Ev$.

One may also show that the invariant $-Et + px$ for an arbitrary x, t such that x/t is not v is the same as $-E t_a + p x_a$ where $x_a/t_a = v$. Thus one may use the $(x=0, t_0)$ 4-vector in place of an arbitrary (x, t) in the rest frame as the invariant $-Et + px$ is not changed. In other words, the rest frame means a special energy m_0 and no momentum, but there is also a special coordinate system $(x=0, t_0)$ which transforms to x', t' such that $x'/t' = v$.

These ideas may be applied to Lagrangian theory which at first glance would seem to have nothing to do with special relativity with the special coordinate choice $x_a/t_a = v$.

Lagrangian Theory for a Free Particle

We consider Lagrangian theory defined through:

$$p = dL/dv \quad ((7a)) \quad \text{and} \quad E = pv - L \quad ((7b))$$

((7a)) and ((7b)) hold for both the relativistic free particle Lagrangian $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ and the nonrelativistic one $.5mvv$.

In the above section based on special relativity we argued there exists a special x,t set such that $x/t=v$. In the rest frame, this 4-vector is $(x=0,t_0)$. Thus:

$P = dL/dv = dL/dx \cdot dx/dv$ where $x=vt$ and $dx/dv = t$ so: $p = dL/dx$ where Lt is the free particle action. ((8))

Thus $Lt = px + B(E,t)$ ((9))

Next, one may use ((7b)): $E = pv - L$ so: $Lt = -Et + pvt = -Et+px$ ((10)) which is consistent with ((9))

In other words the free particle action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) is the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ if one uses the special coordinate system x,t such that $x/t = v$. In general an arbitrary x,t which applies to a free particle does not yield $x/t=v$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that there exists a special frame for a particle with a rest mass, namely the rest frame in which there is no velocity or momentum. If viewed from a constant moving frame, the particle moves and so has momentum, velocity and a new energy. We assume $p=Ev$ in such a case. For a free moving particle, one may have any x,t pair. If one suggests that a matrix transforms $(p=0, E=m_0)$ into $(p=Ev, E)$ then there is a special (x,t) pair, namely $(x=0, t_0)$ which transforms in the same way i.e. x changes a $v t'$ so that $x'/t' = v$. Not every x,t pair, however, has the property $x/t=v$ and a free particle may be associated with any such pair. We suggest that one may write an arbitrary $(x,t) = (x=0,t) + (x,0)$. We then suggest that consider the transformation matrix of the form:

$$\begin{vmatrix} a & av \\ va & a \end{vmatrix}$$

and seek a metric such that $(p,E) \cdot (x,0)$ is 0. In such a case, an arbitrary (x,t) behaves as (x_a,t_a) with $x_a/t_a=v$ in the dot product. We find that $-Et+px$ satisfies this criterion. Thus the special form (x_a,t_a) such that $x_a/t_a =v$ is linked to the general form at least as far as $-Et+px$ is concerned

Next we consider both free particle relativistic and nonrelativistic Lagrangians based on $p=dL/dv$ partial and $E=pv-L$. We use $p=dL/dv =dL/dx \cdot dx/dv$ with $x=vt$ so $dx/dv = t$. $d(Lt)/dv = p$ so $L=px+B(E,t)$. $E=pv-L$ leads to $Lt = -Et+px$ which is the Lorentz invariant which may be treated with $x/t =v$. We have already shown in (2) that if one writes $v=x/t$ in the relativistic/nonrelativistic Lagrangian forms, one obtains the same result.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Special Relativity, Lagrangian Theory and Quantum Mechanics (preprint, zenodo,2022)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Klein-Gordon Equation, $\exp(i\text{Action})$ [Propagator] and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo,2021)